

The Riemann hypothesis may be true twice.

Author: Dante Servi ORCID: 0000-0002-8664-3415

I have no doubt that the Riemann hypothesis is true and I like to say that may be true twice.

The purpose of this revision [v02] is to correct the error present in version [v01].

I report the error, how I discovered it and how I have correct it.

The formulation (1 b), object of the correction, concerns negative prime numbers, maybe they are not useful but I think they can exist.

How the error occurred: I used the function $\text{sum}(n=1, nf, \text{expr})$ of PARI-GP with the intention of forcing it to perform the summation of negative (n), but I wrote $\text{sum}(n=1, nf, -n^s)$.

I should have written $\text{sum}(n=1, nf, (-n)^s)$, this would have forced PARI-GP to change the sign of (n) before performing the exponentiation.

I realized my error when I decided to try to obtain an equivalent result, using the first part of the equality known as Euler's product.

I thought I'd simplify the problem by trying to use whole numbers instead of complex numbers (Euler's original version) and I found a solution using appropriate multipliers and/or divisors.

I then returned to the formulation (1 b) and as I have done for over three years, I used PARI-GP for the calculations and a two-dimensional CAD to connect the points and study the resulting traces.

I chose to initially limit the traces to the first ten segments (from PARI-GP I get the results converted into coordinate for the Cartesian plane), I compared the resulting traces from $\sum_{n=1}^{n=10} \frac{1}{n^s}$ for $s=1/2+i$ with the traces resulting from $\sum_{n=1}^{n=10} (-n)^s$ for $s=-1/2+i$.

The comparison showed that the traces resulting from the second formulation were (overall) reduced and rotated, so an appropriate multiplier was needed for the final result of the summation.

Once I found the multiplier, I does a fair number of tests using different values for both (a) and (b), obviously I performed the comparison with the traces resulting from $\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s}$

These are the command lines for PARI-GP, I add that they work correctly.

When in doubt, I recommend increasing the precision of the calculation.

```
Z(f, s)=sum(n=1, f, (-n)^s)*(-1/(-1)^s)
```

```
a=-1/2
```

```
b=
```

```
s=a+b*I
```

```
f1=0
```

```
f2=round(b/Pi)
```

```
for(f=f1,f2, print(real(Z(f, s)) ", " imag(Z(f, s))))
```

The required data is a value (which I propose positive) for (b), obviously (a), (f1) and (f2) can also be changed, there is a reason for the proposed value for (f2). I highlight that $f1=0$ is used to get 0,0 as the first coordinate.

The result is the Cartesian coordinates of the points resulting from the increment of (n) from (f1) to (f2), this is the formatting needed to obtain the trace from a two-dimensional CAD.

Below I provide the link to the manuscript where, in appendix I explain how to use the CAD.

This is the correct version of the formulation (1 b).

$$\frac{(-1)^s}{-1} \zeta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} (-n)^s$$

Here are some examples of traces that can be obtained in the way I have described, I compared them with the traces resulting from the original Riemann zeta function ($\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s}$).

On the left I put the traces resulting from the formulation (1 b), on the right I put the traces resulting from the original Riemann zeta function. I used values of (b) known as zeros of the Riemann zeta function.

I corrected the activity I posted on geogebra.org which uses the formulation (1 b), the number of vectors is limited to 70 but allows you to vary both (a) and (b) permitting you to observe what influence the values of (a) and (b) have on the trace, this even outside the critical strip.

Below I provide the link to this activity and also the link to a previous activity of mine that uses the original Riemann zeta function, which I call formulation (1) in the manuscript I discuss below.

The Riemann Hypothesis.

In 1859 the great German mathematician Bernhard Riemann, in one of his manuscripts, he presented a new version of Euler's product. The innovation introduced by Riemann, was to use for (s) the complex numbers. He further hypothesized that, all "non-obvious" zero of his version of the zeta function, are complex numbers with the real part $1/2$. Exist only one point that defines the "non-obvious" zero and this point is the origin of the complex plane. In this manuscript I consider only the "non-obvious" zero.

The "non-obvious" zero resulting from the formulation (1 b) are complex number with the real part $-1/2$, so it is specular with respect to $1/2$ with reference to the imaginary axis.

How I became convinced that the Riemann hypothesis is true.

For any formulation of the Riemann zeta function, at each increment of (n) a new point is defined on the complex plane. I analyzed the resulting traces by joining these points, using PARI-GP and a two-dimensional CAD.

In a manuscript published on zenodo.org I explain how I obtained the results and provide the tools to verify them. The manuscript does not contain a rigorous (formal) mathematical proof, however I maintain that what I state is true and verifiable.

Functions (4), (5), (6), (7) and (8) derive from understanding the results obtained with PARI-GP, results that I analyzed and understood thanks to the tools made available by the CAD.

I have carried out (over almost three years) many other tests from which I have always obtained confirmation of the validity of these five functions, but also of the others that I have derived from them.

These are the links that always refer to the latest revision of the manuscript in question.

Original Italian version. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026728>

English translated version. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026759>

These are links to two activities I posted on geogebra.org, the first one uses the formulation (1 b) while the second one uses the original Riemann zeta function.

<https://www.geogebra.org/m/cbkhpgv4>

<https://www.geogebra.org/m/bwypnxvx>

Dante Servi
Via Palmiro Togliatti, 14
Bressana Bottarone (PV) Italy
dante.servi@gmail.com